

Nambicuara

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Entry tags: Religious Group, South American Religions

The Nambicuara are an indigenous society residing in what is now the state of Mato Grosso, Brazil. This entry focuses on ethnographic evidence collected during fieldwork with the Cocozu subgroup around 1940, at which time missionaries had been present in the region for about a decade (Boglár, 2010:4). Considered by outsiders to be fierce and aggressive, the Nambicuara had very little contact with non-indigenous peoples until the end of the 19th century, at which time anthropologist Luiz Boglár made the first ethnographic description of the group (Boglár, 2010:1). At the time and place this entry focuses on, Nambicuara religion centered around potentially dangerous spirits and a basic and ubiquitous concept of power believed to be present in living beings and inanimate objects. Shamans were relied on to appease and propitiate the supernatural beings (Boglár, 2010:4-5). For the Nambicuara, religious beliefs were inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life. Therefore, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large.

Date Range: 1925 CE - 1950 CE

Region: Cacozi group, ca. 1940

Region tags: South America, Brazil

Cacozi group, Brazil, ca. 1940

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, George P. 1962-1971. *Ethnographic Atlas*. *Ethnology* 1-10.
- Source 3: Murdock, George P., and Suzanne F. Wilson. 1972. "Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-cultural codes 3." *Ethnology* 11, no. 3: 254-295.
- Source 1: Ross, Marc Howard. 1983. "Political Decision Making and Conflict: Additional Cross-Cultural Codes and Scales." *Ethnology* 22, no. 2: 169-192.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sp17-001>

- Source 1 Description: Lévi-Strauss, Claude, and Eileen Sittler. 1948. *Family and Social Life of the Nambikwara Indians*. Paris: Société des Américanistes.
- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sp17-000>
- Source 1 Description: Boglár, Luiz. 2010. "Culture Summary: Nambicuara." New Haven, Conn.: Human Relations Area Files.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sp17-003>
- Source 2 Description: Lévi-Strauss, Claude. 1945. "The Social and Psychological Aspect of Chieftainship in a Primitive Tribe: The Nambikuara of Northwestern Mato Grosso." *Transactions of the New York Academy of Sciences, Series II Vol. 7*: 16–32.
- Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sp17-002>
- Source 3 Description: Lévi-Strauss, Claude. 1948. "The Nambicuara." In *Bulletin*, 361-369 , 2 end plates. Washington: Smithsonian Institution.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "... in 1933 a Protestant mission was installed not far from the post on the Juruena" (Lévi-Strauss and Sittler, 1948:142).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), "Internal warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year (original code 5)" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), "External warfare seems to occur every year, but usually only during a particular season (original code 4)" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Membership is consequently assumed to be assigned at birth.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Therefore, it is assumed that the religion has political support.

Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– I don't know

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 757, Political and Religious Differentiation, there is some overlap between political and religious leaders (Ross, 1983; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 2000

Notes: "I take this figure [20,000 as estimated in 1915] as greatly exaggerated, but even if reduced by one half, it considerably exceeds the present number which is hardly more than 2,000" (Lévi-Strauss, 1945:19).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "[The shaman] is distinguished by having the privilege of polygyny, playing the leading role in ceremonial life, and possessing special supernatural powers" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:369).

Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "[The shaman] is distinguished by having the privilege of polygyny, playing the leading role in ceremonial life, and possessing special supernatural powers" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:369).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972, Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures), "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972:259, 272; note: equivalent to SCCS Variable 66).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that personhood is not extinguished with death of the physical body: "Men's souls are believed to be reincarnated as jaguars, whereas women's and children's souls are taken away by wind and thunder, never to return" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:368).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Men's souls are believed to be reincarnated as jaguars, whereas women's and children's souls are taken away by wind and thunder, never to return" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:368).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The souls of the dead are thought to linger about the grave for a few days before finally departing to the rocky hill that the Nambicuara consider their original homeland" (Boglár, 2010:5).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: "The souls of the dead are thought to linger about the grave for a few days before finally departing to the rocky hill that the Nambicuara consider their original homeland" (Boglár, 2010:5).

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "Men's souls are believed to be reincarnated as jaguars . . ." (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:368).

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: "Men's souls are believed to be reincarnated as jaguars . . ." (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:368).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that adherents' corpses are given special treatment. See questions below for details.

Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "The eastern groups [including Coccozu] practice double interment. The bodies are first placed in a crouching position . . . in a circular ditch . . . seven feet deep heaped up with earth and branches. . . . Then [after decomposition] they [washed bones] are carried in a cloth to be permanently buried in the village" (Lévi-Strauss and Sittler, 1948:129).

Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: "The eastern groups [including Coccozu] practice double interment. The bodies are first placed in a crouching position . . ." (Lévi-Strauss and Sittler, 1948:129).

Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale, "secondary contact with the body or bones is the preferred means of disposal for all or nearly all adult members of the society" (Schroeder, 2001; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: "Weapons, implements, adornments, and other property of the deceased are destroyed . . ." (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:367).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "Then they are carried in a cloth to be permanently buried in the village. The village is then abandoned, but the site is often visited" (Lévi-Strauss and Sittler, 1948:129).

Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: "Then they are carried in a cloth to be permanently buried in the village. The village is

then abandoned, but the site is often visited" (Lévi-Strauss and Sittler, 1948:129).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of non-human supernatural beings. See questions below for details.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, a supreme high god is "Absent or not reported" (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of previously human spirits.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of non-human supernatural beings, known as ata'su: "There are also dangerous spirits of the bush and of water, which may appear in the shape of an animal, especially the jaguar, or in a particular form of their own" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:368). However, these supernatural beings are not described in significant detail. See Lévi-Strauss, 1948:368-369 and Lévi-Strauss and Sittler, 1948:115 for more information.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Association with death

Notes: "Death is identified with these spirits" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:368).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of supernatural monitoring.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The Nambikwara have a sharp sense of tradition" (Lévi-Strauss and Sittler, 1948:137).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of sex restrictions.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of sex restrictions.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: "... the jaguar can be hunted and killed, and its remains are highly regarded since the hide is used to make the fur bonnets worn in the attire of war; but it is not eaten under any pretext" (Lévi-Strauss and Sittler, 1948:115).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: "The initiation rite for young men consists of piercing their lips and nose and giving them their adult personal name" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:367).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of small-scale medical rituals, but does not that these rituals are required for membership: "More complicated disorders require intervention by the shaman, who uses herbs and the sucking out of the evil from the victim's body. To appease the spirit causing the illness, he must also chant, as he must win the assistance of the spirit in order to discover the cause of the illness" (Boglar, 2010:5). See Lévi-Strauss and Sittler, 117-118 for more information.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "The Nambikwara have three types of ceremonies. Those which mark the critical moments of each one's existence, such as birth, initiation, puberty, marriage, death; the seasonal festivals; and finally, the ceremonies celebrated on exceptional occasions: war and hunting or scavenging expeditions" (Lévi-Strauss and Sittler, 1948:119).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of multiple extra-ritual in-group markers, including food taboos, traditional dress and hairstyles, ornamentation, ritual language, piercings, and body painting. See questions below for details.

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: ". . . the jaguar can be hunted and killed, and its remains are highly regarded since the hide is used to make the fur bonnets worn in the attire of war; but it is not eaten under any pretext" (Lévi-Strauss and Sittler, 1948:115).

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: "[Hair] is cut with a shell, either all around the head at the level of the ear lobe, or only across the forehead, the back and sides being allowed to fall loose" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:365).

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: "Both sexes are naked, except that men sometimes tie a small tuft of buruty straw to their belt to cover the sex organs" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:364).

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: "Both men and women wear a thin, cotton-thread belt strung with white or black beads cut from river mollusk shells or from tucumã palm nuts. Such beads, with larger triangular pieces of mollusk shells, are also used for necklaces, earrings, bracelets, and other ornaments" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:364).

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: "Groups not acquainted with each other used ritual speech when they met" (Boglar,

2010:4).

Other:

– Yes [specify]: Piercing

Notes: "The initiation rite for young men consists of piercing their lips and nose and giving them their adult personal name" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:367).

– Yes [specify]: Body painting

Notes: "Body painting consists mainly of urucú smeared uniformly, but some groups roughly trace black dots and stripes with genipa juice on the chest and legs" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:365).

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: "Sometimes also [the discrimination between fictive and consanguineal or affinal kin] seems useless because . . . the theoretical wife can become a real wife (for example in case of polygamy, or of remarriage), the theoretical father or mother, or the theoretical son or daughter, can play the role of true father or mother, or of true son or daughter, through the mechanism of adoption" (Lévi-Strauss and Sittler, 1948:23).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: The Nambicuara do not have jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Murdock and Wilson (1972, Column 10: Descent) indicate that the Nambicuara have bilateral descent without kindreds. Additionally, the Nambicuara live in agamous communities without localized clans, lineal kin groups, or exogamy (Murdock, 1962-1971, columns 19, 20, 22). Information on jurisdictional hierarchy and kin ties indicates that the Nambicuara are most accurately characterized as a band.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates an absence of transportation infrastructure: "Canoes are unknown. Small waterways are crossed on a fallen tree; large ones by swimming, sometimes with the help of large floating bundles of buri palm stems" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:365).

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates an absence of transportation infrastructure: "Canoes are unknown. Small waterways are crossed on a fallen tree; large ones by swimming, sometimes with the help of large floating bundles of buri palm stems" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:365).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: According to Ross (1983, Variable 29: Taxation), "Individuals in the society pay no taxes" (Ross, 1983:180, 183; note: equivalent to SCCS Variable 784).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 90, Police, police functions among the Nambicuara are not specialized (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1 [of Cultural Complexity] - Writing and Records, the Nambicuara do not possess a distinct written language (Murdock and Provost, 1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: "The year is divided into two seasons and an undetermined number of lunar months. The day includes six main stages, each based on the position of the sun" (Lévi-Strauss, 1948:369).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society itself, this entry assumes that the religious group provides food for itself. The Nambicuara depend primarily on gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) and extensive or shifting agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation) providing secondary means of subsistence. Fishing (SCCS Variable 205, Dependence on Fishing) supplements the diet (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Nambicuara depend primarily on gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) and extensive or shifting agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation) providing secondary means of subsistence. Fishing (SCCS Variable 205, Dependence on Fishing) supplements the diet (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).